

Kinetics and Mechanism of Bromine Oxidation of Coordinated Formate

PURNA CHANDRA RATH and NIROD KUMAR MOHANTY*

P. G. Chemistry Department, Sambalpur University, Jyotivihar-768 017 (Orissa)

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The kinetics and mechanism of bromine oxidation of formatopentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate have been investigated. The rate of loss of bromine was found to be first order in [substrate] and [bromine]. The observed second order rate constant, k_{obs} for decrease of bromine is given by the expression,

$$k_{obs} = k/[Br^-][H^+]$$

HOBr seems to be the active oxidant species. The values for the rate and activation parameters have been computed and a possible mechanism has been suggested.

THE mechanism of bromine oxidation of several substrates has been studied by several workers¹⁻⁴.

In case of the oxidation of substituted mandelic acids¹, isobutyraldehyde² and esters³ by bromine, molecular bromine was reported to be the oxidant species while for mandelic acid⁴ both Br_2 and HOBr were claimed to be the active oxidant species. Literature survey indicates that the bromine oxidation of a coordinated substrate has not been undertaken as yet. In the present investigation bromine oxidation of formatopentaamminecobalt(III) ion has been undertaken to understand the mechanism of the reaction and to establish the active oxidant species.

Experimental

Formatopentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate was prepared by the method of Price and Taube⁵. The purity of the complex was checked by estimating cobalt as described in literature⁶. To estimate formate in the complex, 0.1 g of the complex was boiled with a solution of sodium hydroxide. The oxide of cobalt was filtered off through a Gooch crucible. The residue was washed several times with distilled water. The filtrate and washings were diluted to 100 ml. The amount of formate in the solution was estimated by titrating with standard potassium permanganate solution as mentioned in literature⁷. Anal. calc. for $(NH_3)_5CoOCOH(ClO_4)_2$: Co, 15.2; $HCOO^-$, 11.6 per cent. Found: Co, 15.1; $HCOO^-$, 11.4 per cent. All the solutions were prepared from reagent grade chemicals. Sodium perchlorate and sodium bromide solutions were standardised by ion exchange method using 50 WX-8 cation exchange resin. Acetic acid was standardised with standard alkali and sodium acetate of known concentration was prepared by neutralizing standard acetic acid with standard sodium hydroxide solution. The bromide concentration was adjusted

with sodium bromide solution and the ionic strength was adjusted with sodium perchlorate solution. The pH of the reaction solution was maintained with acetate-acetic acid buffer. Water used throughout the experiment was deionised water distilled from alkaline potassium permanganate solution.

Stoichiometry: A stoichiometry of one mole of oxidant to one mole of substrate was found by carrying out the reaction with 4 to 5 fold excess of bromine.

Kinetics of the Reaction: The kinetics was followed by estimating the unreacted bromine iodometrically. Preliminary experiments indicated that iodine did not react with formate complex under these conditions. To avoid photo catalysis, if any, the reaction was studied in flasks painted black.

Results and Discussion

The reaction was studied under second order conditions and the observed second order rate constant, k_{obs} , and its least squares deviation were computed with the help of the IBM 1130 computer of Utkal University. Preliminary experiments indicated that the reaction rate remained unaffected with a variation of ionic strength. In subsequent runs, therefore, the ionic strength was not maintained. The second order rate constant was found to be invariant with either the [substrate] or [oxidant] (Table 1).

Bromine in presence of bromide ion is known to exist in form of Br_2 , Br_3^- and HOBr. The reaction rate (at a constant pH) was found to be retarded (Table 2) with an increase of $[Br^-]$ indicating that Br_3^- is not the oxidant species. Further, the reaction

* For correspondence.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [COMPLEX] AND [BROMINE] ON THE SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT

	Temp. = 50 ± 0.1°C, pH = 4.4 and [Br ⁻] = 0.2M						
[Complex] × 10 ³ (M)	4.0	6.0	8.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
[Bromine] × 10 ³ (M)	4.0	6.0	8.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0
k _{obs} × 10 ³ (M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	0.98	1.11	1.10	1.24	1.17	1.34	1.41
	(±0.02)	(±0.04)	(±0.03)	(±0.04)	(±0.08)	(±0.08)	(±0.05)

rate at constant [Br⁻] increased with increasing pH (Table 3). The effect of pH and [Br⁻] on the reaction rate can be explained by assuming HOBr to be the reactive oxidant species which is formed by the hydrolysis of Br₂ :

K'₁ has been reported⁸ to be of the order of 10⁻⁸ at 25° indicating [HOBr] << [Br₂]_{total}. Further the temperature range (50-60°) maintained in the present investigation being high, the [Br₂]_s may also be regarded to be small. It follows, therefore, that

$$[\text{Br}_2]_{\text{T}} \approx [\text{Br}_2]_{\text{f}}$$

(where [Br₂]_T is total bromine and [Br₂]_f is free bromine concentration).

The equilibrium constant K'₁ is given by

$$K'_1 = \frac{[\text{HOBr}][\text{H}^+][\text{Br}^-]}{[\text{Br}_2]_{\text{T}}[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{and } [\text{HOBr}] = \frac{K_1[\text{Br}_2]_{\text{T}}}{[\text{H}^+][\text{Br}^-]} \quad (3)$$

(where K'₁[H₂O] = K₁)

If HOBr is assumed to be the active oxidant as per the following reaction

the rate of the reaction is given by

$$\text{Rate} = k_1[\text{complex}]_{\text{T}}[\text{HOBr}] \quad \dots (4)$$

(where [complex]_T = total complex concentration).

Substituting for [HOBr] from eq. 3 in eq. 4 it follows that

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_1 K_1 [\text{complex}]_{\text{T}} [\text{Br}_2]_{\text{T}}}{[\text{H}^+][\text{Br}^-]} \quad \dots (5)$$

The observed second order rate constant k_{obs} is, therefore, given by

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k}{[\text{H}^+][\text{Br}^-]} \quad (6)$$

(where k = k₁K₁)

If HOBr be the reactive species, it follows from equation 6 that the plots of k_{obs} vs 1/[Br⁻] at constant [H⁺] and k_{obs} vs 1/[H⁺] at constant [Br⁻] should be linear and should yield the same value of k as have actually been observed (Tables 2 and 3). The values of k (using eq. 6) and its least squares deviation have been presented in Tables 2 and 3.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [BROMIDE] ON OBSERVED SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT

pH = 4.4			
Temp. (°C)	[Br ⁻] (M)	k _{obs} × 10 ³ (M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	k × 10 ⁷ (M sec ⁻¹)
50 ± 0.1	0.1	2.23 ± 0.06	0.92 ± 0.07
	0.2	1.24 ± 0.01	
	0.4	0.50 ± 0.00	
	0.5	0.37 ± 0.01	
55 ± 0.1	0.1	3.42 ± 0.10	1.32 ± 0.25
	0.2	2.32 ± 0.06	
	0.3	1.21 ± 0.06	
	0.4	1.03 ± 0.02	
60 ± 0.1	0.5	0.77 ± 0.02	2.8 ± 0.40
	0.1	7.70 ± 0.26	
	0.125	6.35 ± 0.15	
	0.17	4.71 ± 0.14	
	0.25	3.35 ± 0.04	
	0.5	1.97 ± 0.02	

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF pH ON OBSERVED SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT

[Complex] = 3 × 10 ⁻³ M, [Bromine] = 3 × 10 ⁻³ M and [Br ⁻] = 0.2M			
Temp. (°C)	pH	k _{obs} × 10 ³ (M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	k × 10 ⁷ (M sec ⁻¹)
50 ± 0.1	5.6	23.1 ± 0.02	1.17 ± 0.1
	5.2	11.43 ± 0.01	
	4.8	3.26 ± 0.03	
55 ± 0.1	4.4	1.24 ± 0.01	1.9 ± 0.12
	4.4	2.32 ± 0.06	
	4.0	0.82 ± 0.03	
	3.6	0.28 ± 0.00	
	3.0	0.11 ± 0.00	

The activation parameters for the bromine oxidation of the formate complex calculated from Eyring equation and the corresponding least squares deviation have been collected in Table 4. The

TABLE 4—RATE AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Temp. (°C)	k (M sec ⁻¹) × 10 ⁷	ΔH* (k cal/mole)	ΔS* (e.u.)
50 ± 0.1	0.92 ± 0.07(*), 1.17 ± 0.1(**), 1.00 ± 0.12(***)	21.1 ± 0.2	-(25.5 ± 0.3)
55 ± 0.1	1.32 ± 0.25(*), 1.9 ± 0.12(**), 1.79 ± 0.22(***)		
60 ± 0.1	2.8 ± 0.4(*)		

* k values from Table 2.

** k values from Table 3.

*** Average values of k.

entropy of activation is found to be negative indicating that the activated complex is more ordered. This is probably due to the fact that there is a complex formation between the substrate and oxidant

in the transition state. The nature of the complex may be similar to one suggested by Hayakawa and Sato⁹ for iodine oxidation of formate. The present experimental results can be explained with the help of the following mechanism :

Saffir and Taube¹⁰ have pointed out that one electron oxidants like Ce(IV), Mn(III) etc. remove an electron from coordinated oxalate in $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoOCOCOOH}]^{2+}$ and internal electron transfer to Co^{III} centre occurs reducing it to Co^{II} while two electron oxidants like H_2O_2 [catalysed by Mo(VI)] and Cl_2 simultaneously remove both the electrons from coordinated oxalate preserving oxidation state of cobalt; $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{OH}_2)]^{3+}$ being formed as the oxidation product. Candlin and Halpern¹¹ have established that in MnO_4^- oxidation of formate complex, both Co^{2+} and $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}(\text{OH}_2)]^{3+}$ were the products of oxidation and the latter is formed from a reaction intermediate of the type A shown in the above reaction scheme. In the present study since the bromine is a two electron oxidant it is expected that the oxidation state of cobalt should be preserved. In fact an attempt has been made to detect

the presence of Co^{2+} in the reaction solution by using the method of Kitson¹². Since Co^{2+} is not formed as product we presume the formation of $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}(\text{OH}_2)]^{3+}$ ion as the reaction product.

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